

PERIOPERATIVE APPROACH AND NURSING PRACTICES IN CARDIAC EMERGENCY SURGERY WITH CURRENT GUIDELINES

Keywords

Cardiac emergency surgery,

Perioperative care,

ERAS guidelines,

Evidence-based practice,

Patient safety,

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ABSTRACT

Due to the high mortality rate in cardiac emergency surgeries, skilled nursing care at all stages of the surgical process is critical for patient safety and recovery. This study aims to examine evidence-based practices and nursing approaches in cardiac emergency surgeries, guided by guidelines. Preoperatively, safety-based practices such as patient identification, informed consent, allergy assessment, and surgical site marking are paramount. Intraoperatively, practices such as sterility, patient positioning, vital sign monitoring, and instrument counting are prominent. Postoperatively, essential practices include pain control, vital monitoring, wound and drain monitoring, as well as early diagnosis of complications, mobilization, and discharge education. Literature demonstrates that the active role of nurses throughout all surgical stages improves patient outcomes and reduces complication rates. Therefore, the study focuses on evidence-based practices in line with guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

Cardiac emergencies, while rare in surgical procedures, are critically important due to their high mortality rates. These conditions are characterized by sudden deterioration in the patient's vital functions and present with clinical conditions requiring rapid intervention.¹ Cardiac emergencies can arise from a variety of causes, including penetrating trauma, cardiac surgery, or complications arising from non-cardiac surgeries.² These complications can be fatal, and the most common reasons for the high mortality rates of cardiac emergencies include failure to recognize deterioration in the patient's vital parameters in a timely manner and inadequate interventions.³ Hypovolemia, myocardial dysfunction, and pulmonary embolism are among the leading causes of cardiac arrest, particularly in the perioperative period. Cardiac arrest is most frequently reported to occur within the first 48 hours after surgery, particularly in non-cardiac surgeries. The frequency of cardiac complications, particularly within the first 48 hours, highlights the importance of effective basic and advanced life support practices, as well as the quality of perioperative care.⁴ For these reasons, early intervention based on evidence-based practices and multidisciplinary teamwork, in which nurses play a key role, are recommended for the effective management of cardiac emergencies.⁵ ERAS (Enhanced Recovery After Surgery) is believed to be beneficial in cardiac emergency surgeries because it consists of protocols that include evidence-based practices and require multidisciplinary teamwork.

This review provides a detailed overview of preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative care practices in cardiac emergencies, in light of current ERAS (Enhanced Recovery After Surgery) protocols. The review aims to improve patient safety, reduce complications, and highlight evidence-based guideline recommendations through a multidisciplinary approach to address these critical surgical situations

Volume: 1

Issue: 2

Page: 27-34

Received: 27.04.2025

Accepted: 13.07.2025

Available online: 03.08.2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16652518

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1. Perioperative Approach in Cardiac Emergencies with Current Guidelines

1.1. Preoperative Period

The preoperative period requires a detailed preoperative assessment of the patient and, if necessary, the development of supportive care plans. During this phase, the patient's current medical condition is assessed in terms of the risks that may be encountered during surgery. ⁶The following points should be considered in this assessment:

Patient Anamnesis

When taking an anamnesis, the following should be taken into consideration: ^{6,7,8}

Medical History: The patient's previous surgeries, chronic diseases (e.g., diabetes, hypertension, heart diseases), and allergies.

Medications Used: Especially the presence of medications such as blood thinners, antihypertensives, insulin, anticonvulsants.

Family History: Presence of genetic diseases in the family.

Alcohol, Smoking and Substance Use: Use case for potential risks associated with anesthesia.

Physical Examination

Physical examination should pay attention to: ^{6,7,8}

Vital Signs: Blood pressure, pulse, respiratory rate, temperature, and oxygen saturation.

General Condition: The patient's general physical condition, mental state, and pain level.

Heart and Lung Examination: Condition of the cardiac and pulmonary systems, respiratory distress or rhythm disturbances.

Abdominal Examination: Intra-abdominal pathologies, acute abdomen findings.

Wound and Infection Status: If there is a trauma, whether the wound is infected or not, bleeding status, etc.

Laboratory Tests and Imaging

Blood Tests: Complete blood count (CBC), kidney function tests (BUN, creatinine), Liver function tests, Electrolyte balance (sodium, potassium), Coagulation tests (INR, aptT) Glucose levels ^{6,7,8}

Radiological Evaluation: Chest X-ray (especially for patients with cardiopulmonary problems), abdominal ultrasound, or computed tomography (CT) should be performed if necessary. ^{6,7,8}

Anesthesia Evaluation

Before surgical interventions, anesthesia is administered to ensure the patient feels no pain or discomfort and to ensure the necessary surgical conditions. The primary goal of specialists is to maintain the patient's circulatory system, mean arterial pressure, and oxygen saturation at optimal levels. The goal is to use minimal anesthesia to ensure rapid neurocognitive recovery and minimize side effects such as nausea and vomiting. This allows the recovery process to begin immediately after surgery and progress proactively. ⁹In this context, the following conditions should be evaluated. ^{6,7,8}

Anesthesia Risk: The patient's suitability for anesthesia is determined by the ASA (American Society of Anesthesiologists) classification.

Airway Assessment: Whether endotracheal intubation is required and whether the patient's airway is open.

Pharmacological Risks: Drug interactions and medication management required for anesthesia

Cardiovascular Risks: Hypertension, heart diseases, arrhythmia, history of myocardial infarction.

Pulmonary Risks: Asthma, COPD, history of pulmonary embolism.

Other Risks: Presence of systemic diseases such as diabetes, kidney failure, obesity.

Psychological Status: Presence of anxiety, depression, stress situations.

Social Support: The patient's support situation at home and care needs.

Urgency of Surgery: This determines whether urgent surgical intervention is necessary. When urgent surgical intervention is necessary, the letter "E" is added after the patient's classification number, such as ASA IE.

Alternative Treatment Options: Evaluation of whether non-surgical treatment methods, if any, can be applied.

Early diagnosis of the disorder and intervention

For patients requiring urgent surgery, diagnostic interventions should be performed in conjunction with surgical preparation. This process includes improving the patient's condition (timely antibiotic prophylaxis, fluid resuscitation, medication omission/alternative route use, nutrition, glycemic control) , providing timely imaging reports, reducing delays in emergency surgery, recognizing high risk (triage), using sound principles, obtaining informed consent, and informing the family. ¹⁰⁻¹²

Anesthesia and intraoperative management

To minimize the risk of aspiration after anesthesia induction, rapid airway control and intubation using the rapid-acting muscle relaxant suxetylcholine (1–2 mg/kg) or rocuronium (0.9–1.2 mg/kg) are recommended. Drugs used for anesthesia induction should be selected and administered at appropriate doses to maintain hemodynamic stability (**Level of evidence: Moderate; Grade of recommendation: Strong**).³³ Monitoring the depth of anesthesia is recommended in patients aged 60 years and older who are at risk for postoperative delirium and anesthesia-induced hypotension (**Level of evidence: Moderate; Grade of recommendation: Strong**).³³ Core temperature measurement and monitoring the effectiveness of warming measures are recommended to reduce the risk of hypothermia during the intraoperative period (**Level of evidence: High; Grade of recommendation: Strong**).³⁴ Active warming devices and warming of intravenous fluids are also recommended to maintain normothermia (**Level of evidence: High; Grade of recommendation: Strong**).³⁵

Intravenous fluid and electrolyte management

Resuscitation before, during, and after surgery is critical for the management of patients undergoing emergency surgery. Fluid overload can lead to perioperative complications such as organ dysfunction, ventilator dependence, and delayed wound healing.³⁶ Inadequate fluid intake can lead to poor organ perfusion and renal failure. Patients should receive ongoing treatment to correct electrolyte disturbances during the perioperative period (**Level of evidence: Medium Recommendation rating: Strong**).³⁷ It is recommended that in high-risk patients, current dynamic hemodynamic therapy should be considered during surgery to optimize cardiac index and that a Cardiac Index of [2.2 L/min/m²] should be targeted during surgery (**Level of evidence: Medium Recommendation rating: Strong**).³⁸ Red blood cell transfusion should be limited (triggering Hb 70–90 g/L); exceptions should be determined according to the clinical situation and comorbidities.^{38,39} Patients' glucose levels should be closely monitored and controlled within the range of 7.7–10 mmol/L, preferably with a variable-rate insulin infusion. (**Level of evidence: Medium Recommendation rating: Strong**).³⁹

End of surgery, evaluation and endotracheal extubation

Patients undergoing emergency surgery are at high risk for

postoperative pulmonary complications (PPC). Therefore, a multidisciplinary discussion at the end of surgery is recommended to assess the appropriateness of endotracheal extubation due to the high risk of postoperative pulmonary complications and reintubation (**Level of evidence: Moderate ; Grade of recommendation: Strong**).⁴⁰ In a study of 30,000 patients conducted in light of this recommendation, the highest risk factors for patients requiring reintubation within the first 3 days were an ASA physical status score (PS) of III or higher (OR 5.23), emergency surgery (OR 4.21), and high-risk procedures such as abdominal surgeries. Reintubation increases the in-hospital mortality rate by 72-fold. Furthermore, another study of 6,063 patients identified 13 perioperative risk factors associated with the risk of postoperative pulmonary complications, including older age, a high ASA PS score, emergency surgery, and surgery lasting longer than 1 hour.⁴¹

1.3 Postoperative care

The postoperative period is the time that begins after a surgical procedure and continues until the patient is fully recovered. This period can vary depending on the type of surgery, the patient's general health, and the complexity of the procedure. The primary goals of the postoperative period are to support the patient's recovery, minimize the risk of infection and complications, provide pain management, and enable functional rehabilitation.³¹ The duration and management of the postoperative period vary depending on the type of surgery performed. Comprehensive follow-up is required, and patient adherence to instructions plays a crucial role in accelerating the recovery process.⁴² To this end,

Patients undergoing emergency surgery who have hypoxemia (low oxygen levels) are recommended to receive CPAP (continuous positive airway pressure) or NIPPV (non-invasive positive pressure ventilation) instead of standard oxygen therapy if they are at low risk of pulmonary aspiration. This practice is recommended in an environment where personnel skilled in these techniques are available, continuous physiological monitoring is available, and arterial blood gas samples can be obtained (**Level of Evidence: High; Level of Recommendation: Strong**).⁴³

It is recommended that patients aged 65 years and older undergo regular postoperative delirium screening, and that patients at risk be managed with nondrug

interventions such as regular referrals, sleep hygiene approaches, and cognitive stimulation to prevent delirium, while drug triggers should be minimized (**Level of evidence: High; Level of recommendation: Strong**).^{40,44}

Patients should be assessed for VTE risk with a validated tool upon admission and throughout their hospital stay. If pharmacologic prophylaxis is not feasible, mechanical prophylaxis should be administered. For very high-risk patients (patients undergoing emergency surgery), pharmacologic and mechanical prophylaxis should be administered concurrently. Assessment should be performed daily postoperatively (**Level of evidence: High; Level of recommendation: Strong**).^{45,46}

Urinary catheter use should be evaluated daily and the catheter should be removed as early as possible. (**Level of evidence: Moderate; Level of recommendation: Strong**).⁴²

Early tube feeding (within 24 hours) should be initiated in patients who cannot be started on early oral feeding and whose oral intake will be inadequate for more than 7 days. (**Level of evidence : Moderate; Level of recommendation: Strong**).⁴⁶

If enteral nutrition is contraindicated, early parenteral nutrition is necessary to alleviate the period of inadequate oral/enteral intake. Once gastrointestinal function is restored and/or contraindications cease, enteral or oral feeding should be resumed, and parenteral nutrition should be discontinued when caloric needs can be safely met by oral/enteral routes.

(**Level of evidence: Moderate; Level of recommendation: Weak**)⁴⁶

A multimodal approach is recommended to minimize postoperative ileus; this approach should include minimally invasive surgery, optimized fluid management, opioid-avoiding multimodal analgesia, early mobilization, early postoperative food intake, laxative administration, and early removal/removal of nasogastric intubation. (**Level of evidence: Moderate; Level of recommendation: Strong**).^{46,47}

Patients should be mobilized as soon as possible after Surgery (**Level of evidence: Weak; Level of recommendation: Strong**).^{46,47} as contaminated or puncture wounds and gunshot wounds.

2. Nursing Practices in Cardiac Emergencies

Nursing practices in cardiac emergencies include the following items:⁴⁹⁻⁶¹

A primary assessment should be made quickly. Primary assessment;

A. Airway: Assess consciousness.

B. Breathing: Assess breathing.

C. Circulation: Evaluate pulse and circulation signs and symptoms.

D. Defibrillation: Assess the rhythm.

A secondary evaluation should be conducted after the primary evaluation. The second evaluation is:

Circulation: IV access is established, and fluids and medications are administered. Cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) is continued. Medication appropriate to the evolving cardiac rhythm is administered.

Airway: Advanced airway control is achieved. Endotracheal intubation is performed.

Breathing: Ventilation is performed using an appropriate endotracheal intubation tube. Positive pressure ventilation is applied.

Differential Diagnosis: Possible causes of arrest are investigated. Specific treatment is applied based on these causes.

The patient's vital signs are monitored frequently. The state of consciousness is checked according to the GCS.

If there is a bleeding area, bleeding should be controlled if possible.

The patient should be placed supine, the lower extremities elevated at a 30-degree angle, and the knees straight. Should have at least two vascular accesses with the widest lumen possible.

If peripheral vascular access cannot be established, a central vascular access should be established.

If there are any prosthetic teeth, they should be removed.

If blood or mucus is present, it should be aspirated.

Cases with respiratory arrest or severe hypoxemia should be intubated and ventilation should be provided with 100% oxygen.

If shock develops due to bleeding, 7-8 liters/minute oxygen should be given via nasal mask.

Respiratory rate and rhythm should be monitored continuously.

The amount of fluid given should be 2.5-3 times the amount of fluid lost.

If necessary, blood transfusion should be performed.

Laboratory tests should be performed. Samples are taken for cardiac enzymes and other necessary blood tests.

The patient should be monitored.

A 12-lead ECG should be obtained.

The patient's vital signs should be monitored frequently.

The patient should be monitored with a Foley bladder catheter and urine output should be monitored.

The ordered medications must be administered completely.

During shock, oral intake should be stopped and an NGS should be inserted for gastric lavage.

Body temperature should be checked frequently and maintained.

The patient's relatives should be warned and complete information about the patient should be obtained.

The patient should not be left alone.

It is recommended to maintain mean arterial pressure above 65 mmHg.

Prophylactic antibiotics are administered intravenously approximately 30 minutes before surgery. If the surgery is more than 3 hours away, an additional interim dose may be necessary.

Dexamethasone 8 mg is administered intravenously 90 minutes before anesthesia induction to reduce postoperative nausea and vomiting and also to improve the inflammatory response.

To reduce anxiety, routine use of sedatives before surgery should be avoided.

The area where the surgical procedure will be performed should be shaved with an electric razor or hair removal cream as close as possible to the operation.

Risk factors for perioperative hypothermia are assessed.

Patients at risk for IPD should be identified, and risk factors should be identified and documented. Patients with body temperatures below 36°C should be actively warmed.

Active treatment should be started immediately if body temperature increases exceed 1.5°C.

In order to ensure cardiac output in the postoperative period, the patient's vital signs and blood pressure should be monitored **every 15 minutes in the first hours, as they may deteriorate due to conditions such as bleeding,**

hematoma, pain, and hypoxia.

The patient is encouraged to engage in deep breathing exercises and early mobilization to manage ventilation imbalance and maintain airway patency.

Medium-flow, double-lumen oxygen therapy is recommended for the first 48 hours postoperatively. Low flow oxygen therapy or intermittent oxygen therapy is recommended starting on postoperative days 3-5.

Traditionally, normovolemia should be achieved with a fluid regimen of 1–2 ml/kg/hour or 20 ml/kg/24 hours after surgery, and the patient should be encouraged to take oral intake by stopping IV intake as soon as possible.

Regular pain assessment should be performed and appropriate analgesic should be selected.

In the treatment of acute pain, in addition to pharmacological treatment, non-pharmacological methods such as massage, cold and heat application, TENS application, listening to music and hypnosis should also be used.

Oral intake should be started within 2 hours after surgery.

Soft solid foods can be introduced 4 hours after surgery, and solid foods or nutritional support liquids can be introduced 8 hours after surgery.

Daily protein intake of 2.0 g and energy of 25-30 kcal per kilogram should be provided.

Iron, vitamin B12, calcium and folic acid levels should be monitored regularly.

Straining during bowel movements should be avoided, as this can lead to inadequate blood flow to vital organs. If necessary, a glycerin enema or laxative can be used.

Patients should be given guidance so that they can perform activities such as brushing their teeth, eating, drinking, and changing position on the affected side.

Within 1-3 days after surgery, gradual bed-based exercises of both upper and lower limbs should be performed to prevent venous thrombus embolism (VTE).

Discharge education may be given to the patient if he/she meets the following conditions:

- Oral food intake should be adequate and the need for
- intravenous fluids should be eliminated.
- He/she should not be having respiratory distress
- Pain control should be achieved with oral analgesics.
- Bowel function should have returned.
- Adequate mobilization must be ensured.

- There should be no signs or symptoms of infection.
- The patient must be willing to return home.
- Concomitant diseases must be under control.

CONCLUSION

Cardiac emergency surgeries are clinical situations requiring rapid and effective intervention and carrying a high risk of mortality and morbidity. To improve patient safety and clinical outcomes in these situations, a multidisciplinary, evidence-based approach must be adopted at every stage of the surgical process—preoperatively, intraoperatively, and postoperatively. Current ERAS protocols play a critical role in this context by providing a holistic roadmap encompassing patient assessment, hemodynamic stability, infection control, pain management, nutrition, mobilization, and discharge criteria.

This review emphasizes that nurses are positioned not only as caregivers but also as professionals who play an active role in the early diagnosis and intervention of life-threatening complications. Many aspects of nursing practice, including patient monitoring, use of early warning systems, advanced life support practices, education, and rehabilitation, directly impact patient outcomes in cardiac emergencies.

In conclusion, in the management of cardiac emergency surgery, a multidisciplinary team approach, implementation of current guidelines, a holistic approach aligned with ERAS protocols, and the active participation of nurses can significantly improve patient prognosis. Therefore, the mastery and systematic implementation of these protocols by healthcare professionals, particularly surgical nurses, is crucial for ensuring patient safety, reducing complications, and improving the quality of care.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

Acknowledgements

No

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